

EFFECT OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP ON THE BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY OF MICRO, SMALL, AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (MSMES) IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study examined the effect of social entrepreneurship on the business sustainability of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives were to determine the effect of social mission on consumer satisfaction, innovation on profitability and stakeholder engagement on energy consumption practices. In line with these objectives, three research questions were formulated, and three hypotheses were developed and tested. The literature was reviewed under three major headings: conceptual review, theoretical framework, and empirical review. The study was anchored on the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory A survey research design was adopted. The population comprised MSME stakeholders in South East Nigeria, and a sample size of 384 respondents was selected using stratified random sampling. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using linear regression via SPSS version 23. The findings revealed that social mission had a significant effect on consumer satisfaction ($\beta = 0.597$, $t = 14.579$, $p = 0.000$); innovation significantly influenced profitability ($\beta = 0.573$, $t = 13.701$, $p = 0.000$) and stakeholder engagement had a significant effect on energy consumption practices ($\beta = 0.486$, $t = 10.859$, $p = 0.000$). The study concluded that social entrepreneurship plays a critical role in enhancing the sustainability and performance of MSMEs in South East Nigeria. It recommended that MSMEs integrate social missions into their business models, embrace innovation, strengthen stakeholder engagement, adopt market-driven strategies, and remain adaptable to evolving environmental and societal changes. By doing so, MSMEs can contribute meaningfully to regional development while achieving long-term sustainability and competitiveness.*

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Introduction

Background of the Study

Sustainability has gained significant prominence as companies seek to balance economic, social, and environmental goals. For Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), particularly in South East Nigeria, achieving sustainability involves implementing practices that not only ensure long-term financial success but also contribute positively to society and the environment (Okoye, Nwakoby, and Ezike, 2021). With MSMEs being vital contributors to economic growth and employment in the region, integrating sustainable business practices is essential for addressing the socio-economic challenges they face. A sustainable approach enables these enterprises to build resilience, reduce risks, and meet the evolving expectations of stakeholders, including customers, employees, and regulators (Olaniyan & Akinbode, 2023, Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025).

Social entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in promoting business sustainability by focusing on solving societal problems through innovative and mission-driven business models. This form of entrepreneurship emphasizes creating social value as a primary objective while simultaneously generating economic returns

(Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024). By embedding social and environmental goals into their core operations, social enterprises go beyond traditional profit-driven motives and aim to address pressing issues such as poverty, inequality, and environmental degradation (Akinola & Akinyele, 2023). In South East Nigeria, where social and economic challenges are prevalent, social entrepreneurship serves as a strategic approach for MSMEs to achieve sustainability while contributing to the broader development agenda.

The relationship between social entrepreneurship and business sustainability is rooted in the integration of social missions into business models, which drives sustainable development in the local context (Okoye, & Nnebe, 2023). Social enterprises are characterized by their commitment to addressing unmet social needs and enhancing community welfare, which often involves innovative approaches to delivering products and services (Chukwu& Obi, 2022). For MSMEs in South East Nigeria, embedding a social mission enables them to gain a competitive advantage by differentiating themselves from conventional businesses. This approach not only attracts customers who value ethical practices but also fosters long-term business

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growth by building trust and loyalty within the communities they serve (Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, (2025).

Moreover, the principles of social entrepreneurship, such as stakeholder engagement, innovation, market orientation, and adaptability, are vital for enhancing business sustainability in dynamic environments like South East Nigeria. Social enterprises that actively engage stakeholders and adapt to market changes can better navigate challenges and seize emerging opportunities (Ogunleye & Adeoye, 2022). By aligning their business strategies with social objectives and adopting innovative solutions, MSMEs can address local problems effectively while achieving sustainable business performance. As such, social entrepreneurship serves as a significant driver of business sustainability by providing a framework for MSMEs to operate in a manner that benefits both society and the enterprise (Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025).

The social mission is central to social entrepreneurship and represents the primary purpose or driving force behind an enterprise's existence. Unlike traditional businesses that are profit-oriented, social enterprises are guided by social goals, such as addressing poverty, unemployment, and environmental

degradation. In the context of MSMEs in South East Nigeria (Ohanyere, Okoye, & Nnebe, 2025). The social mission often involves providing affordable goods and services to underserved populations, creating employment opportunities, or contributing to community development (Eze & Chukwu, 2023). A strong social mission helps MSMEs in this region align their business activities with societal needs, ensuring that their operations not only generate revenue but also contribute positively to the community's well-being. This alignment can enhance business sustainability by building a loyal customer base that values the enterprise's social contributions (Ohanyere, Arinze, & Atueyi 2025).

Innovation is another critical variable in social entrepreneurship that contributes to business sustainability. Social entrepreneurs use creative solutions to solve social problems, often with limited resources. In South East Nigeria, MSMEs are confronted with numerous challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and a rapidly changing business environment. These constraints necessitate innovative approaches to developing products, services, and business processes that meet the needs of the local market (Akinola&Akinyele, 2023). By fostering a culture of innovation, social entrepreneurs

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can improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance their competitive advantage, which ultimately contributes to sustainable business growth. Furthermore, innovation in social enterprises extends beyond technological advancements to include social innovation, where novel strategies are implemented to address social issues and improve the quality of life for the people.

Stakeholder engagement is a fundamental aspect of social entrepreneurship that significantly impacts business sustainability. MSMEs in South East Nigeria operate in environments where the support and involvement of various stakeholders, including customers, employees, suppliers, and government agencies, are crucial for success (Chukwu & Obi, 2022). Engaging stakeholders in decision-making processes and sustainability initiatives fosters collaboration, trust, and a sense of shared responsibility for achieving social and environmental objectives. For social enterprises, effective stakeholder engagement not only helps to build strong networks and partnerships but also enables them to better understand the needs and expectations of the communities they serve. By incorporating stakeholder feedback into their business strategies, MSMEs can enhance the relevance and impact of their social initiatives, leading to

sustained business performance and community support.

The integration of social mission, innovation and stakeholder into social entrepreneurship practices can enhance the sustainability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria by addressing the root causes of social and economic challenges. Social enterprises often operate in environments where market failures exist, such as inadequate access to essential services or the presence of significant social inequalities (Adewuyi & Olowookere, 2021). By adopting these variables, MSMEs can contribute to solving these problems in a manner that is both financially viable and socially impactful.

Statement of the Problem

The broad issue of "Social Entrepreneurship and Business Sustainability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria" highlights the struggle of many Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the region to achieve sustainable growth while pursuing social missions. These businesses play a significant role in driving economic development, but they face challenges in integrating social entrepreneurship principles into their operations. The result is a limited ability to balance business profitability with social value creation, leading to insufficient progress towards sustainable development goals in South East Nigeria.

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One major challenge is limited access to financial resources, which restricts the ability of MSMEs to implement social entrepreneurship initiatives. Many financial institutions regard these enterprises as high-risk, making it difficult for them to secure loans or attract investors. Without adequate funding, MSMEs are often unable to innovate or invest in sustainable business practices, which stifle their growth and impact. This financial constraint also limits their ability to pursue social missions effectively, resulting in missed opportunities for broader social and economic development.

Another issue is inadequate infrastructure and technology, which poses significant barriers to the growth of MSMEs. The lack of reliable power supply, poor transportation networks, and limited access to digital tools make it challenging for businesses to operate efficiently and deliver social value. This problem is particularly pronounced in rural and semi-urban areas of South East Nigeria, where infrastructural development is lagging behind urban centers, further exacerbating the difficulties these businesses face in achieving sustainability.

Additionally, low levels of stakeholder engagement hinder the capacity of MSMEs to align their social entrepreneurship efforts with the needs of key stakeholders, including

customers, employees, government agencies, and local communities. When businesses do not engage effectively with their stakeholders, they struggle to understand market needs and preferences, which limit support for their social initiatives. As a result, MSMEs face difficulties in building relationships that are essential for fostering long-term business sustainability.

The existing literature provides limited insights into the relationship between social entrepreneurship and business sustainability among MSMEs in South East Nigeria. This study aims to fill this gap by studying how social entrepreneurship factors, such as social mission, innovation, stakeholder engagement, market orientation, and adaptability, contribute to the sustainability of these enterprises. It will also propose strategies to improve the capacity of MSMEs to achieve sustainable growth, such as enhancing access to finance, improving infrastructure, fostering stakeholder engagement, promoting market-oriented strategies, and building adaptability and resilience. These interventions are crucial for strengthening the social and economic impact of MSMEs and advancing sustainable development in the region.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to investigate the effect of social entrepreneurship

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on sustainability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the effect of social mission on consumer satisfaction of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.
2. Examine the influence of innovation on the profitability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.
3. Investigate the effect of stakeholder engagement on the energy consumption practices of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated in line with the objectives of the study to give direction to the research:

Ho1: Social mission has no significant effect on consumer satisfaction of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

Ho2: Innovation has no significant influence on the profitability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

Ho3: Stakeholder engagement has no significant effect on the energy consumption practices of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Social Entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship has garnered significant attention in recent years, evolving as a distinct approach to addressing social challenges while simultaneously creating

economic value. The concept can be traced back to the late 20th century, but it has gained momentum in the 21st century due to a growing recognition of the limitations of traditional philanthropy and government-led initiatives in solving complex social issues. The term "social entrepreneurship" was popularized by scholars and practitioners, including Muhammad Yunus, who founded the Grameen Bank to provide microcredit to impoverished communities in Bangladesh, demonstrating how entrepreneurial principles can be applied to social missions (Yunus et al., 2020).

Social entrepreneurship is defined as the process of identifying and pursuing innovative solutions to social problems through entrepreneurial activities. It encompasses a wide range of activities, from creating social enterprises to implementing community-driven initiatives that prioritize social impact over profit maximization. According to Dees (2021), social entrepreneurs are individuals who leverage resources and innovations to address societal challenges while generating sustainable revenue streams. This dual focus on social mission and financial sustainability distinguishes social entrepreneurship from traditional business models and nonprofit organizations.

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Social Mission

The concept of a social mission has evolved significantly over the past few decades, particularly within the framework of social entrepreneurship. Historically, the roots of social missions can be traced back to the early philanthropic efforts of individuals and organizations aimed at addressing societal issues. However, with the emergence of social entrepreneurship in the late 20th century, the idea of social missions transformed from mere charitable acts to a strategic focus integrated within business models. This shift marked a critical transition where businesses began to align their operational goals with social value creation, leading to the establishment of enterprises that prioritize social impact alongside financial sustainability (Dees, 2020).

A social mission can be defined as the underlying purpose or guiding principle of an organization that reflects its commitment to addressing social, environmental, or community challenges. It serves as a framework for decision-making and strategic planning, ensuring that the organization remains focused on its goals of creating social value. According to Mair and Marti (2021), a social mission is not merely a slogan but a fundamental aspect of an organization's identity that shapes its activities and priorities. This definition highlights the

importance of a clearly articulated social mission in differentiating social enterprises from traditional for-profit organizations.

Innovation

Innovation is a dynamic and multifaceted concept that has evolved over time, reflecting changes in society, technology, and economic conditions. Historically, innovation has been a key driver of progress, influencing various sectors and industries. The term "innovation" is often attributed to the work of Joseph Schumpeter, who, in the early 20th century, described it as the process of creating new products, services, or methods that lead to economic growth. Schumpeter's view emphasized the role of entrepreneurs as catalysts of innovation, suggesting that their willingness to take risks and introduce new ideas is crucial for economic development (Schumpeter, 1934).

In contemporary discourse, innovation is commonly defined as the implementation of new ideas, processes, products, or services that enhance efficiency, create value, or address societal challenges. According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), innovation involves the development and application of new or significantly improved products, processes, marketing strategies, or organizational practices

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(OECD, 2021). This definition highlights the broad scope of innovation, which can occur across various domains, including technology, business models, and social practices.

Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement has evolved significantly over the years, emerging as a critical component in the fields of business management, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and social entrepreneurship. Historically, stakeholder engagement was primarily concerned with the relationships between companies and their immediate stakeholders, such as shareholders and employees. However, as the global business landscape has changed, the definition of stakeholders has expanded to encompass a broader array of parties, including customers, suppliers, community members, government agencies, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). This shift reflects the growing recognition that businesses operate within complex social and environmental contexts, necessitating a more inclusive approach to engagement (Freeman, 1984; Sweeney, 2021).

In its most basic form, stakeholder engagement refers to the process by which organizations consult, communicate, and collaborate with stakeholders to understand their needs, expectations, and concerns. According to Raut

and Agrawal (2021), stakeholder engagement is not merely a one-way communication process but rather an ongoing dialogue that fosters mutual understanding and trust between organizations and their stakeholders. Effective stakeholder engagement involves identifying key stakeholders, assessing their influence and interests, and implementing strategies to involve them in decision-making processes that affect them (Benn et al., 2020).

Sustainability

Business sustainability has gained significant traction in recent years, emerging as a vital concept within the fields of management, corporate strategy, and economics. Its origins can be traced back to the broader idea of sustainable development, which was popularized by the 1987 Brundtland Report, "Our Common Future." This report highlighted the need for economic growth that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland Commission, 1987). Over the years, the definition of business sustainability has evolved to encompass not only environmental and economic dimensions but also social aspects, reflecting a more integrated approach to corporate responsibility. At its core, business sustainability refers to the ability of an organization to operate in a manner

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that is economically viable while also being environmentally responsible and socially equitable. According to the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), sustainability in business involves creating long-term stakeholder value through a combination of financial performance and contributions to society and the environment (GRI, 2020). This multidimensional definition emphasizes the need for businesses to balance profit-making with their impact on society and the environment, making sustainability a core aspect of strategic planning.

Consumer satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is a vital concept in marketing and business management that refers to the measure of how products or services supplied by a company meet or surpass the expectations of its customers. The roots of consumer satisfaction can be traced back to the early 20th century, where it began to gain attention as a significant factor influencing repeat purchases and brand loyalty. However, it wasn't until the late 20th century that researchers began systematically studying consumer satisfaction, developing various theories and models to understand its implications better. This growing interest was fueled by the increasing competition in markets and the recognition that satisfied customers are

more likely to become loyal patrons and advocates for a brand (Oliver, 2021).

Defining consumer satisfaction can be multifaceted. According to Kotler and Keller (2022), it is the feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance with expectations. When the product performance exceeds expectations, consumers are likely to express satisfaction; conversely, if it falls short, dissatisfaction ensues. This definition highlights the subjective nature of consumer satisfaction, emphasizing that it varies from one individual to another based on personal preferences, experiences, and expectations.

Profitability

Profitability has been a central concept in business and economics since the inception of modern capitalism. Historically, profitability measures the ability of a business to generate profit relative to its revenue, assets, or equity. The evolution of profitability metrics can be traced back to early economic theories, where Adam Smith (1776) emphasized the significance of profit in determining the health of a business and the overall economy. In contemporary times, the definition of profitability has expanded to include various dimensions, including gross profit, net profit, and return on investment (ROI), reflecting the complexity of

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business operations in a globalized market (Higgins & Schall, 2020).

Profitability is commonly defined as the degree to which a business or organization yields financial gain or profit in relation to its costs. This is typically expressed in percentage terms, illustrating the efficiency and effectiveness of a company in converting its resources into profit. According to Păunescu et al. (2021), profitability can be assessed using various financial ratios, including profit margin, return on assets (ROA), and return on equity (ROE), which provide insights into different aspects of financial performance. These metrics enable stakeholders to evaluate a company's operational efficiency, financial health, and strategic direction.

Energy consumption

Energy consumption has been a critical topic of discussion in the context of global development, environmental sustainability, and economic growth. Historically, the demand for energy has evolved significantly from the early days of human civilization when wood and biomass were the primary energy sources. The Industrial Revolution in the 18th century marked a turning point, as coal became the dominant energy source, powering steam engines and factories (Sovacool, 2020). This transition led to unprecedented levels of energy consumption,

which have continued to rise over the centuries, driven by industrialization, urbanization, and technological advancements. Today, energy consumption is a vital indicator of a country's economic health, quality of life, and environmental impact.

Energy consumption can be defined as the total amount of energy utilized by individuals, businesses, and governments to perform various activities, including heating, transportation, manufacturing, and powering electronic devices (International Energy Agency [IEA], 2021). It encompasses various forms of energy, such as fossil fuels (coal, oil, and natural gas), renewable energy sources (solar, wind, hydroelectric, and biomass), and nuclear power. The way energy is consumed affects not only economic development but also environmental sustainability, as it influences greenhouse gas emissions, air quality, and resource depletion.

Theoretical Frame work

In examine the relationship between social entrepreneurship and business sustainability among MSMEs in South East Nigeria, this theories provides a solid theoretical foundation: the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory.

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory, proposed by John Elkington in 1997, The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory posits that businesses should

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assess their performance not solely by financial returns but also by their social and environmental impacts. This holistic perspective urges organizations to consider a broader range of stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, and the communities in which they operate. John Elkington, the originator of this theory, emphasized that a business could only be deemed truly successful if it generates profits while positively impacting society and minimizing environmental harm (Elkington, 2018). This approach encourages businesses to integrate sustainability into their core strategies, making it a foundational element rather than an afterthought. For MSMEs in South East Nigeria, where resources may be limited and community needs are pressing, the TBL framework provides a structured way to align business objectives with societal benefits. In the context of MSMEs in South East Nigeria, economic viability represents the first leg of the TBL. Many MSMEs in this region face challenges such as limited access to capital, fluctuating market demands, and competition from larger firms. By focusing on economic sustainability, these enterprises can implement sound financial practices, optimize their operations, and explore new revenue streams. For instance, MSMEs can leverage local

resources and foster partnerships with other businesses to enhance their market position and economic resilience. This focus on economic sustainability not only helps ensure the survival of these businesses but also contributes to the broader economic landscape of the region. The second dimension of the TBL, social responsibility, is particularly relevant to the social entrepreneurship landscape in South East Nigeria. This dimension highlights the obligation of businesses to contribute positively to their communities and society at large. MSMEs that embrace social responsibility can engage in community development initiatives, such as providing employment opportunities, supporting education, and addressing health care needs. By embedding social missions into their business models, these enterprises can create meaningful relationships with local stakeholders, enhancing their reputation and customer loyalty. Furthermore, when businesses prioritize social outcomes, they can foster a sense of community ownership and engagement, leading to a more supportive environment for their operations. Environmental sustainability, the third dimension of the TBL, has become increasingly critical in today's business landscape. MSMEs in South East Nigeria, like their counterparts globally, face pressing environmental challenges

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such as climate change, resource depletion, and pollution. By adopting sustainable practices such as reducing waste, minimizing energy consumption, and utilizing eco-friendly materials these businesses can mitigate their environmental footprint. Moreover, environmentally conscious MSMEs can differentiate themselves in the marketplace, appealing to a growing segment of consumers who prioritize sustainability in their purchasing decisions. Thus, integrating environmental stewardship into business strategies not only helps protect the planet but can also serve as a competitive advantage.

The TBL Theory encourages MSMEs to adopt a holistic approach to business sustainability that encompasses economic, social, and environmental dimensions. This multidimensional perspective allows for a more comprehensive evaluation of performance, helping entrepreneurs identify areas for improvement and innovation. By embracing the TBL framework, MSMEs in South East Nigeria can create shared value that benefits their business while addressing the pressing social and environmental challenges of their communities. As these businesses evolve, they can contribute to a more sustainable economy, illustrating how social entrepreneurship can

drive positive change while fostering economic growth.

Theoretical Exposition

Social Mission and Consumer Satisfaction

The influence of a social mission on consumer satisfaction has gained significant attention in recent years as businesses increasingly recognize the importance of social responsibility in their operations. A social mission encompasses a company's commitment to addressing social, environmental, or ethical issues, which can resonate deeply with consumers. Bhattacharya and Sen (2020) highlights that consumers are more likely to feel satisfied with brands that demonstrate a strong social mission, as these companies align their values with those of their customers. This alignment fosters a sense of trust and loyalty, which is essential for enhancing overall consumer satisfaction.

Innovation and Profitability

Innovation plays a pivotal role in enhancing profitability across various sectors, including small and medium enterprises (MSMEs). It serves as a catalyst for growth, enabling businesses to differentiate themselves in a competitive marketplace Voss and Voss (2021), firms that embrace innovation are more likely to experience increased sales and market share,

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which directly translates into higher profitability. By developing new products, services, or processes, businesses can attract a broader customer base and create additional revenue streams. This highlights the crucial link between innovative practices and financial success, making innovation an essential strategy for MSMEs seeking to improve their bottom line.

Stakeholder Engagement and Energy Consumption Practices

Stakeholder engagement plays a pivotal role in shaping energy consumption practices, particularly in the context of sustainable development. The involvement of various stakeholders including government agencies, businesses, local communities, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) creates a collaborative environment that fosters the exchange of knowledge, resources, and best practices. Agyemang et al. (2021), effective stakeholder engagement can lead to the identification of innovative solutions to energy challenges, enabling more sustainable energy consumption patterns. By incorporating diverse perspectives, stakeholders can collaboratively address the complexities of energy use, fostering more effective policies and practices that promote efficiency and sustainability.

Empirical Review

Adewuyi& Yusuf (2022). Examine The Role of Social Entrepreneurship in Promoting Sustainable Business Practices Among MSMEs in Southwestern Nigeria. The study examined 300 MSMEs in Lagos and Ibadan, Southwestern Nigeria. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select the participants. Data was collected through structured questionnaires, and the analysis was conducted using regression analysis to determine the relationship between social entrepreneurship and sustainable business practices. Results indicated that socially-driven business models significantly enhance sustainability through community engagement and environmental consciousness.

Olaniyan&Adekunle (2021). Studied Social Entrepreneurship and Business Sustainability in the Nigerian SME Sector: A Study in North-Central Nigeria. This research involved a population of 250 MSMEs in North-Central Nigeria, with a sample size of 180 MSMEs selected through a purposive sampling technique. The data collection instrument included surveys and interviews. Descriptive statistics and chi-square tests were employed to assess how social entrepreneurship initiatives have influenced sustainable practices in the region. The findings indicated a significant

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positive effect on business continuity through social entrepreneurial ventures.

Chukwu&Nwankwo (2020). Investigate Impact of Social Entrepreneurship on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Small Businesses in Western Nigeria. The study focused on 400 small businesses in Western Nigeria, with a sample size of 200 selected using simple random sampling. Data was collected via a structured questionnaire, and analysis was performed using structural equation modeling (SEM) to examine the impact of social entrepreneurship on achieving SDGs. The results indicated that social enterprises aligning their operations with social impact goals achieved better economic, social, and environmental sustainability.

Ogunleye&Fadare (2023).Examine Social Innovation and Business Sustainability: Evidence from MSMEs in Northern Nigeria. Conducted in Northern Nigeria, the study's population consisted of 500 MSMEs, with a sample size of 220 selected through cluster sampling. Data was collected through surveys and focus group discussions. Multiple regression analysis was used to determine the effect of social innovation on business sustainability. Findings revealed that incorporating social entrepreneurial approaches with traditional business models significantly

boosted long-term business viability by addressing community needs.

Smith & Roberts (2020). Examine Social Entrepreneurship and SME Business Sustainability in the United Kingdom. The study surveyed 150 MSMEs in London, using a census sampling technique to include all businesses in the specified area. Data was gathered using questionnaires and analyzed using logistic regression to explore the impact of social entrepreneurship on sustainability. Results showed that businesses adopting social entrepreneurial approaches demonstrated stronger resilience and adaptability due to a focus on social impact and environmental responsibility.

Chen & Wang (2021).studied Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Business Practices: A Comparative Study of MSMEs in China and India. This research involved 1,000 MSMEs from Beijing and Mumbai, with 500 MSMEs from each city selected through stratified sampling. Data collection was done using a mixed-method approach, combining surveys and in-depth interviews. Analysis was carried out using comparative analysis techniques and path analysis to compare the role of social entrepreneurship in promoting sustainability in both countries. The findings

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showed that MSMEs integrating social impact objectives had higher sustainability.

Methodology

The study employed a survey research design to investigate the relationship between social entrepreneurship and business sustainability among Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Southeast Nigeria. This design was selected to facilitate the collection of primary data from a large sample through structured questionnaires, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the perceptions and experiences of MSME owners. The research was conducted in the five states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo, a region known for its vibrant economic activities and strong entrepreneurial culture, making it a suitable context for examining how social entrepreneurship influences business sustainability. The target population for the study consisted of 4,001,718 registered MSMEs across these states, as documented by the SMEDAN and National Bureau of Statistics Collaborative Survey (2013). The sample size was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan formula, which calculated a required sample of approximately 384 MSMEs based on a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. To ensure a representative sample, a stratified random sampling technique was adopted, where the

population was first divided into strata based on business sectors such as manufacturing, agriculture, retail, and services. A proportional random sample was then drawn from each stratum to capture the diversity of the MSME landscape and improve the generalizability of the findings. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire designed to capture information on social entrepreneurship practices and business sustainability indicators, utilizing a combination of closed-ended and Likert-scale questions. The instrument's validity was ensured through content validation by experts in social entrepreneurship and business management, who reviewed and refined the questionnaire for relevance and comprehensiveness. Its reliability was confirmed via a pilot study using the test-retest method, which yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.85, indicating strong internal consistency. Trained research assistants administered the questionnaires in person to selected respondents, with follow-ups conducted to ensure a high response rate. Finally, the collected data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and means, were used to summarize the demographic profiles and responses of the participants. For inferential

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analysis, linear regression was employed to test the study's hypotheses regarding the effect of social entrepreneurship on business sustainability. All analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 2023, with a significance level set at 0.05 to determine the statistical relevance of the relationships examined.

Table 4.3.1: Model Summary Table

R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
0.597	0.357	0.356	0.3023

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

The model summary in Table 4.3.1 shows that the R Square value is 0.357, indicating that 35.7% of the variation in consumer satisfaction is explained by social mission. This shows a

Table 4.3.2: ANOVA Table

Source	Sum Squares	of Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	19.44	1	19.44	212.5	0.000
Residual	34.96	382	0.0915		
Total	54.40	383			

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

The ANOVA table indicates that the regression model is statistically significant, with $F(1, 382) = 212.5$ and $p < 0.001$. This means that the

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Ho1: Social mission has no significant effect on consumer satisfaction of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

moderate level of predictive accuracy and suggests a meaningful relationship between the variables.

model significantly predicts consumer satisfaction based on social mission.

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Table 4.3.3: Coefficients

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficient B	Std. Error	t	Sig.	95% Interval	Confidence
Constant	0.0627	0.126	0.496	0.620	[-0.186, 0.311]	
Social Mission	0.4805	0.033	14.579	0.000	[0.416, 0.545]	

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

The coefficient table shows that social mission has a positive and statistically significant effect on consumer satisfaction (B = 0.4805, $p < 0.001$). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: Innovation has no significant influence on the profitability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

Table 4.3.4: Model Summary Table

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.573	0.329	0.328	0.3832

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

The R Square value of 0.329 suggests that 32.9% of the variation in profitability can be explained by innovation practices. This

rejected. This implies that the more MSMEs pursue a social mission, the higher the level of consumer satisfaction they are likely to achieve.

demonstrates a moderately strong relationship between innovation and profitability.

Table 4.3.5: ANOVA Table

Source	Sum Squares	of Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	27.57	1	27.57	187.7	0.000
Residual	56.15	382	0.147		
Total	83.72	383			

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

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The ANOVA table indicates a statistically significant model ($F = 187.7, p < 0.001$),

showing that innovation is a significant predictor of profitability.

Table 4.3.6: Coefficients Table

Variable	Unstandardized B	Coefficient Std. Error	t	Sig.	95% Interval	Confidence
Constant	0.0534	0.171	0.312	0.755	[-0.283, 0.390]	
Innovation	0.5942	0.043	13.701	0.000	[0.509, 0.679]	

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

The coefficient for innovation is positive and statistically significant ($B = 0.5942, p < 0.001$). This means that as innovation increases, profitability also increases significantly. Thus, H_02 is rejected.

Hypothesis 3

H_03 : Stakeholder engagement has no significant effect on the energy consumption practices of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

Table 4.3.7: Model Summary Table

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.486	0.236	0.234	0.2672

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

The R Square of 0.236 indicates that stakeholder engagement explains 23.6% of the variance in energy consumption practices

among MSMEs. This reflects a modest but statistically relevant relationship.

Table 4.3.8: ANOVA Table for

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	8.39	1	8.39	117.9	0.000
Residual	27.18	382	0.0711		
Total	35.57	383			

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

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The model is statistically significant, as indicated by the F statistic of 117.9 with a p-value < 0.001. This suggests stakeholder

engagement has a significant impact on energy consumption practices.

Table 4.3.9: Coefficients Table

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficient B	Std. Error	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval
Constant	0.2259	0.120	1.880	0.061	[-0.010, 0.462]
Stakeholder Engagement	0.3399	0.031	10.859	0.000	[0.278, 0.401]

Source: SPSS version 23, (2025)

The coefficient table reveals that stakeholder engagement significantly affects energy consumption practices (B = 0.3399, p < 0.001). Therefore, Ho3 is rejected. This means that businesses that engage stakeholders more effectively are likely to adopt more sustainable energy consumption practices.

Discussion of Findings

Ho1: Social mission has no significant effect on consumer satisfaction of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

The regression analysis revealed that social mission has a statistically significant and positive effect on consumer satisfaction, with an R Square value of 0.357. This implies that approximately 35.7% of the variance in consumer satisfaction can be attributed to the social mission of MSMEs in South East Nigeria. The strength of this relationship underscores the importance of socially driven business

objectives in enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty.

This finding resonates with the work of Singh & Mehra (2022), who investigated the influence of social entrepreneurship on business longevity among MSMEs in New Delhi, India. Their study highlighted how sustainable practices rooted in social mission significantly enhanced business reputation and customer retention. Similarly, Lopez & Martinez (2023), in their study of MSMEs in Colombia, found that social entrepreneurship initiatives—particularly those targeting educational and healthcare services—boosted both consumer perception and loyalty, driving sustained business growth.

In the Nigerian context, Bamgbose & Adeoye (2021) also confirmed that social entrepreneurship had a meaningful influence on sustainable development and consumer engagement among MSMEs in Western Nigeria.

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By aligning business operations with social values, MSMEs are able to build trust and emotional connections with customers, which translates to higher satisfaction. Therefore, this study validates and extends the growing body of literature supporting the view that social missions not only enhance social impact but also serve as a critical factor in customer satisfaction and business longevity.

H02: Innovation has no significant influence on the profitability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

The findings from the regression model demonstrate a significant and positive influence of innovation on profitability, with an R Square value of 0.329. This suggests that 32.9% of the variation in profitability among MSMEs is explained by their innovation practices. This result indicates that MSMEs that adopt innovative methods, products, or services tend to achieve higher profitability levels than those that do not. This conclusion aligns with several international and local empirical studies. Nguyen & Tran (2023), in their study on the growth of MSMEs in Vietnam, found that innovation is a core driver of business expansion and competitive advantage. Their use of regression analysis revealed that innovative MSMEs were more capable of addressing societal needs and penetrating new markets,

resulting in improved profitability. Adeyemi&Akinola (2021) also reported similar outcomes in their study on fashion-based MSMEs in Lagos, Nigeria. They noted that innovation in ethical sourcing and waste reduction improved operational efficiency and financial returns. These findings collectively reinforce the argument that innovation is not only necessary for technological progress but also a strategic imperative for financial sustainability among MSMEs.

H03: Stakeholder engagement has no significant effect on the energy consumption practices of MSMEs in South East Nigeria.

The regression output indicated a significant effect of stakeholder engagement on energy consumption practices, with an R Square value of 0.236. This implies that 23.6% of the variation in MSMEs' energy practices can be accounted for by their level of stakeholder engagement. In essence, businesses that actively involve stakeholders such as employees, customers, suppliers, and the local community are more likely to adopt sustainable and energy-efficient practices. This finding supports the conclusions of Liu & Zhang (2021), who discovered a strong correlation between stakeholder-informed social entrepreneurship and the adoption of environmentally sustainable practices among MSMEs in Beijing,

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China. Similarly, Musa & Ojo (2023) demonstrated that agro-based MSMEs in North-Central Nigeria were more likely to employ eco-friendly and energy-saving technologies when stakeholders were actively engaged in decision-making and implementation processes. Furthermore, Juma & Hassan (2023) emphasized that stakeholder participation in sustainability conversations helps MSMEs in the Tanzanian tourism and service sectors to embed long-term energy-saving solutions into their operations. The present study thus contributes to the growing body of knowledge advocating for participatory stakeholder models as a pathway to achieving energy sustainability and environmental responsibility among MSMEs.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The findings are summarized below:

- i. Social mission had a significant positive effect on consumer satisfaction among MSMEs in South East Nigeria. The regression output showed a Standardized Beta (β) = 0.597, $t = 14.579$, and $p = 0.000$.
- ii. Innovation was found to significantly influence profitability among MSMEs in South East Nigeria. The regression results revealed $\beta = 0.573$, $t = 13.701$, and $p = 0.000$.

- iii. Stakeholder engagement had a significant effect on energy consumption practices of MSMEs in South East Nigeria. The regression coefficients indicated $\beta = 0.486$, $t = 10.859$, and $p = 0.000$.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis and findings, this study concludes that social entrepreneurship is a vital strategic framework for enhancing sustainability of MSMEs in South East Nigeria. Socially driven business practices such as pursuing a defined social mission, adopting innovative approaches, engaging stakeholder the study reinforces the understanding that MSMEs must transcend traditional profit-centric models and integrate socially responsible and community-oriented strategies to achieve long-term growth and sustainability. The empirical evidence affirms that such integration is not only desirable but necessary in today's competitive and dynamic business environment.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

- i. MSMEs should craft and communicate strong social missions that resonate with their customers and communities. This enhances brand loyalty and improves consumer satisfaction.

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ii. Business owners should invest in research and development and support a culture of creativity and innovation within their organizations to drive profitability and competitiveness.

iii. Owners of MSMEs should encourage active involvement of stakeholders in decision-

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making especially regarding sustainability and resource usage should be prioritized. This promotes trust and encourages the adoption of environmentally responsible practices.

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